

ASTRONOMY

FROZEN WATER RESERVOIRS OF MARS

Vidmachenko A.

*Doctor Phys.-Math. Sci., Professor, Professor of Department of Physics
National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

In 2000, the "Mars Global Surveyor" equipment discovered geological structures on the surface of the planet that could have appeared under the influence of water. Later, it was possible to record a huge ice basin on images of the planet's mountain ranges. To the west of the plains of Utopia, a vast sea may also be hidden beneath the surface of Mars. Almost 80% of the soil layer detected by the radar consists of water ice, as well as frozen CO₂ and sand. The nature of the cracks on the rock with the name "Escher" made it possible to state that its rock was exposed to the long-term action of some liquid. A band of very thin dark vertical plates was discovered by the rover "Opportunity". This rock may have formed when older layers of rock cracked, and mineral-rich water seeped through the cracks and left mineral deposits there. They formed a rock stronger than the surrounding stones. Minerals, cavities left after the dissolution of salts, hematite spherical balls, etc. are visible on the same stone. Carbonic acid salts, which are formed only in the presence of water, were also discovered. Such findings increased the duration of the period of presence of water on the surface of Mars by almost 1 billion years. The ClO₄ perchlorate found there is a very strong oxidizer at elevated temperatures. And being mixed with water, this substance significantly lowers its freezing point. Perchlorate may still allow a small amount of liquid water to form on Mars today. After all, the age of some ravines on the slopes of the mountains could be only 1–2 years.

Keywords: Mars, water reservoirs, geological structures, minerals, perchlorate.

In the summer of 2000, the "Mars Global Surveyor" station discovered geological structures on the surface of the planet [8, 9] that could have arisen only under the influence of powerful water flows. And at the beginning of the fall of the same year, the photographs of the mountain massifs of the planet transmitted from

Mars may have recorded a huge ice reservoir [3], under the ice of which there may be water (Fig. 1, left). This conclusion then made it possible to make an assumption that the age of some ravines on steep mountain slopes could be 1–2 years.

Fig. 1. On the left – a possible frozen body of water on Mars near the equator; in the middle – the image from the rover "Opportunity" shows the "Escher" rock with cracks indicating the long-term action of water; on the right – is an image of thin, dark vertical plates at the edge of a bedrock outcrop (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

And recently it was reported about the discovery of a possible huge sea of frozen water hidden under the surface of Mars [12]. Almost 80% of the found soil layer consists of water ice, as well as frozen CO₂ and sand [2, 14]. It is located below the surface to the west of the Utopia Plain, at approximately mid-latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere. This frozen sea was detected using the "SHARAD" radar of the "Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter". Calculations showed that this frozen reservoir has an ice thickness of 80 to 170 m with a volume of more than 14 thousand cubic kilometers.

The "Spirit" rover explored hard rock outcrops at the foot of the Columbia Mountains. These rocks are

possibly the oldest of all that the rovers have studied during their mission. In October 2004, the rover "Opportunity" discovered new possible signs of traces of water on Mars. The discovery of the unusual "Escher" rock (Fig. 1, middle) was made accidentally while trying to bypass the sand areas in Endurance Crater. The character of the cracks on this rock made it possible to state that this rock was exposed to the long-term action of liquid. But then it was believed that maybe there was not water ice on Mars, but some other kind of ice.

The fact that water could be on the surface of Mars for a long period of time [15, 18, 20, 22, 29, 32] is evi-

denced by many other images taken by the rover "Opportunity". Thus, descending into the Endurance crater on 07/22/2004, the lander also discovered a strip of thin dark plates. They were located on the edge of one of the protrusions of the main underlying rock (Fig. 1, right). It has been suggested that this outcrop is a layer of rock that formed when older layers of rock cracked, and mineral-rich water began seeping through those cracks. Over time, only mineral deposits remained there. And already from them a rock was formed, much stronger than the surrounding stones. That is why the vertical plates were able to remain when the bedrock was eroded.

The same multi-layered stone also shows numerous evidence of the past presence of water. Among them are minerals [30, 31], cavities left after the dissolution of salts, hematite spherical balls, etc. The observational results showed that in the Endurance crater these features spread over several geological layers. This type of find significantly increases the duration of the period of presence of water on the surface of Mars. After all, the formation of such cracks requires the mandatory presence of a water medium. Moreover, it takes a long time for the deposits to be compressed into such

a solid substance. So far, it is difficult to say exactly how long water has been on the surface of Mars. But apparently, it is enough even for life to originate there [13, 21, 24].

Mossbauer's spectrometers were installed on the Spirit and Opportunity rovers of the American Mars Exploration Rover mission. For the first time, they made it possible to obtain the soil composition from the spectra of one of the planets of the Solar System during space [17] research (Fig. 2, left). These spectra made it possible to determine the composition of iron compounds on the surface of Mars. They show the presence of three different iron-bearing rocks. One of them is the mineral olivine. Its existence indicates that it was not subject to erosion and the action of water. The obtained results also indicated the clear possibility of the existence of water on the surface of this planet in the past. So, in 2003, salts of carbonic acid were discovered on Mars for the first time. These compounds are part of many earth minerals. And carbonates are formed only in the presence of water and carbon dioxide. Thus, this discovery strengthened the hypothesis that in the distant past on Mars [6] there should have been large reserves of water (Fig. 2, right).

Fig. 2. On the left – the spectrum of the Mossbauer spectrometer on the Mars Exploration Rover "Spirit" in the Gusev crater (January 17, 2004). On the right – topography map of channel Kasei Valles (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Kasei_Valles_topo.jpg).

From the analysis of the information received from the rovers, it was possible to find evidence of the presence of a moist environment even in the stone "El Capitan" (Fig. 3, left). Sulfates and minerals were also found there (Fig. 3, right), which could only form in the

presence of water. Later, the "Spirit" rover made a similar discovery. He drilled the "Humphrey" stone and noted the presence of voids there, which could only be formed under the influence of water. And in the voids, themselves, deposits of minerals were found, which can form only in the presence of water.

Puc. 3. Left – image from the “Mars Exploration Rover” Opportunity’s panoramic camera shows the “El Capitan” region of the rock outcrop at Meridiani Planum (https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/0/00/PIA05457_modest.jpg). Right – the Mossbauer spectrum made it possible to identify the mineral jarosite $(K, Na, X+1) \cdot Fe_3SO_4 \cdot (OH)_6$ containing hydroxyl in the stone “El Capitan” [10].

All these findings made it possible to announce that the “Opportunity” and “Spirit” missions are successful. New results were also obtained as a result of processing observations with the “OMEGA” spectrometer installed on the “Mars Express” apparatus. With the help of spectra in the visible and near-infrared ranges on the surface of Mars, it was possible to detect areas containing phyllosilicates (water-bearing minerals) and hydrated sulfates (Fig. 4, left). Both of these groups of minerals arise as a result of chemical changes in rocks but differ in the mechanism of formation. Phyllosilicates are formed from igneous rocks during prolonged contact with water. Hydrated sulfates are also formed under the influence of water. Moreover, this action does not necessarily have to be long-lasting. But it is necessary that the water has high acidity. The discovery of

these minerals clearly indicates that water was present on the surface of Mars in the past. However, it is much more difficult to determine when exactly this happened. By combining all the available information and the data obtained by the “OMEGA” spectrometers, the following possible scenario for the appearance of these minerals was proposed. Phyllosilicate-rich sediments formed on Mars during an ancient geological period that ended 3.8-3.5 billion years ago. This conclusion was made on the basis of counting the number of meteorite craters and assessing the degree of their erosion. It is assumed that there was enough water on Mars at that time, and it may even have been present on the surface in liquid form. Later, rocks changed by water were covered by lava fields.

Fig. 4. On the left – the location of phyllosilicates and hydrated sulfates according to the data obtained by the “OMEGA” spectrometer (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>). On the right – map of Mare Boreum (https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/e9/Mare_Boreum_Map.jpg).

Nowadays, erosion has only in some places exposed ancient rocks containing phyllosilicates. This hypothesis explains why areas where phyllosilicates are found are not associated with dry riverbeds and other possible traces of water on the surface of Mars. That is, similar riverbeds could be formed later. Water was present in them for a relatively short time and could not lead to the formation of phyllosilicates. However, in a

later era, hydrated sulfates could be formed. This could have happened when the climate on Mars changed significantly, the amount of water decreased, and it became more acidic. Oceanus Borealis is a hypothetical ocean that may have existed on the surface of Mars in the distant past. According to the models, the Martian polar ocean was partially covered by ice and had water temperatures close to its freezing point. This prevented

the formation of clay, which is an important feature of water bodies on Earth. The image in Fig. 4 (right) covers the Martian surface north of 65° latitude. It includes the northern polar ice cap, about 1,100 km across.

"Mariner-9" in 1972 discovered a strip of sand dunes surrounding polar ice deposits, the length of which in some places is 500 km. The entire ice cap is surrounded by the large plains of Planum Boreum and Vastitas Borealis. Not far from the pole is a large valley, Chasma Boreale, which may have been formed by melting water from the ice cap. An alternative view is that it was created by winds coming from the Pole of Cold. Another notable feature is the gentle rise that was called Olympia Planitia. In summer, a dark "collar" around the residual cap becomes noticeable; this is mainly caused by the dunes. On Fig. 4 (right) also shows several very large craters (Lomonosov and Korolev) and the smaller Stokes crater on a smooth surface with small relief changes [1, 26, 27]. The landing module "Phoenix" landed on 05/25/2008 on Vastitas Borealis and Mare Boreum. The probe collected and analyzed soil samples in an attempt to detect water and determine how hospitable the planet once was for the possible development of life. He remained active until the winter conditions became too severe almost 5 months later. After the mission was completed, it was reported that chloride, bicarbonate, magnesium, sodium, potassium, calcium and possibly sulfate were found in the samples analyzed. Their pH was close to 7.7.

Perchlorate (ClO₄), a very strong oxidizer at elevated temperatures, was also discovered [5]. This was an important discovery because this chemical could be used for rocket fuel and as a source of oxygen for future colonists. In addition, under certain conditions, perchlorate can prevent the development of life. Although some microorganisms can obtain energy from matter through anaerobic reduction. And when mixed with water, this chemical can significantly lower its freezing point. Thus, much direct evidence of the presence of water at this location was found. And perchlorate may even allow the formation of a small amount of liquid water on Mars today. Craters are common in some regions of Mars, and may have formed as a result of seasonal [11, 16, 19, 23] melting of perchlorate ice and caused soil erosion on steep slopes by water [4, 7, 25].

References

1. Banham S.G., Gupta S., Rubin D.M., et al. (2021) A Rock Record of Complex Aeolian Bedforms in a Hesperian Desert Landscape: The Stimson Formation as Exposed in the Murray Buttes, Gale Crater, Mars. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*. 126(4), p. 1-35.
2. Clancy R.T., Nair H. (1996) Annual (perihelion-aphelion) cycles in the photochemical behavior of the global Mars atmosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*. 101(E5), p.12785-12790.
3. Conway S.J., Hovius N., Barnie T., et al. (2012) Climate-driven deposition of water ice and the formation of mounds in craters in Mars' north polar region. *Icarus*. 220(1), p. 174–193.

4. Goldspiel J.M., Squyres S.W. (2000). Ground-water sapping and valley formation on Mars. *Icarus*, 148, 176-192.
5. Hecht M., Kounaves S.P., Quinn R.C., et al. 2009. Detection of Perchlorate and Soluble Chemistry of Martian Soil at the Phoenix Lander Site. *Science*. 325, p. 64-67.
6. Hoffman N. (2000) White Mars: A New Model for Mars' Surface and Atmosphere Based on CO₂. *Icarus*. 146(2), p. 326-342.
7. Howard A. (2000) The role of eolian processes in forming surface features of the Martian polar layered deposits. *Icarus*. 144, p. 267-288.
8. Morozhenko A.V., Vid'machenko A.P. (2004) Polarimetry and Physics of Solar System Bodies. *Photopolarimetry in Remote Sensing: Proceedings of the NATO Advanced Study Institute. Yalta, Ukraine. 20 September - 4 October 2003. -503 p., p 369-384.*
9. Morozhenko A.V., Vidmachenko A.P. (2017) Optical parameters of Martian dust and its influence on the exploration of Mars. *Dust in the Atmosphere of Mars and Its Impact on Human Exploration, Proceedings conf. 13-15 June, Houston, Texas. LPI Contribution No. 1966, 2017, id. 6010.*
10. Morris R. V., Klingelhofer G., Bernhardt B., et al. (2004), Mineralogy at Gusev Crater from the Mossbauer spectrometer on the Spirit rover, *Science*, 305, p. 833-836.
11. Murray B.C., Ward W.R., Yeung S.C. (1972) Periodic Insolation Variations on Mars. *Science*. 180(4086), p. 638-640.
12. Plaut J.J., 228 Picardi G., Safaeinili A., et al. (2007). Subsurface Radar Sounding of the South Polar Layered Deposits of Mars. *Science*. 316 (5821), p. 92-95.
13. Steklov A.F., Vidmachenko A.P. (2019) In what places and what exactly can be the "traces" of life on Mars? 9 ICo on Mars, Pasadena, California, July 22-25, 2019, LPI Co. No. 2089, 6007.
14. Vid'machenko A.P., Morozhenko A.V. (2005) Mapping of the physical characteristics and mineral composition of a superficial layer of the Moon or Mars and ultra-violet polarimetry from the orbital station. 36th Annual Lunar and Planetary Science Conference, March 14-18, 2005, in League City, Texas #1015.
15. Vidmachenko A.P. (1987) Manifestation of seasonal variations in the atmosphere of Saturn. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies*. 3(6), p. 9-12.
16. Vidmachenko A.P. (1994) Variations in the brightness of celestial objects in astronomical observations mount Maidanak. *KPCB* 10 (5), 52-56.
17. Vidmachenko A.P. (2009) Research of the Mars by space vehicles. *Astronomical School's Report*. 6(2), p. 131-137.
18. Vidmachenko A.P. (2009) Water on Mars. *Astron. almanac*. 56, p. 225-249.
19. Vidmachenko A.P. (2015) Seasons on Saturn. II. Influence of solar activity on variation of methane absorption. *Astronomical School's Report* 11 (1), 15-23.

20. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Activity of processes on the visible surfaces of Solar System bodies. *Astronomical School's Report* 12 (1), p. 14-26.
21. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Is there life on Mars and where necessary to search for its traces. *Astronomy and present: materials of 5 Interregional Scientific Conference*. April 12, 2016. Vinnytsia, Ukraine. P. 43-48.
22. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Processes on the "young" Mars: possible developments of events. *18 ISCo AS YS*, Kyiv, Ukraine, May 26-27, 2016. P. 16-17.
23. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Seasonal changes on Jupiter: 1. Factor of activity of the hemispheres. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies* 32 (4), 189-195.
24. Vidmachenko A.P. (2017) Where Should Search Traces of Life, Which Could Appear on Mars in the First 300 Million Years. *Fourth ICo on Early Mars: Geologic, Hydrologic, and Climatic Evolution and the Implications for Life*. 2014. 3005.
25. Vidmachenko A.P. (2018) Comparative features of volcanoes on Solar system bodies. *20 ISPCo AS YS*, May 23-24. Uman, Ukraine, p. 9-12.
26. Vidmachenko A.P. (2018) Modern volcanic activity on the Moon. *20 ISPCo AS YS*, May 23-24, 2018. Uman, Ukraine, p. 5-7.
27. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) Comparison of features of impact and volcanic craters on the surface of Mars. *Proceed. of VIII Intern. Sc. and Pract. Conf. Progr. Res. m. w. (27-29.04.2023)*. Ch. 43. BoScience Publisher, Boston, USA, p. 237-246.
28. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) History of possible climate change on Mars. *Proceedings of VII International Scientific and Practical Conference. Science and innovation of modern world. (23-25 March 2023)*. Chapter 54. Cognum Publishing House, London, United Kingdom, p. 336-345.
29. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) Thermal properties of the surface of Mars. *Proceedings of VII ISPCo. Progressive research in the modern world (March 29-31, 2023)*. Chapter 42. BoScience Publisher, Boston, USA, p. 243-252.
30. Vidmachenko A.P., Klimenko V.M., Morozhenko A.V. (1981) Apparent spectral albedos of the disk of Mars in September-October 1977. *Solar System Research*. 14(4), p. 157-159.
31. Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2020) Mineral resources can be mined on different bodies of the Solar System. *22 ISCo AS YS*, December 11-12, 2020. Kyiv, Ukraine, p. 89-92.
32. Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2022) How long ago has water flowed on Mars surface? Results of modern scientific research and development. *Proceedings of XI ISPCo*. Barca Academy Publishing, Madrid, Spain. 16-18.01.2022. P. 226-232.